

Blood Investigations in Patients with COVID-19 Infection: A Descriptive StudyHaseena B. A.¹, Deepthi Krishnan², Sreeram B.³, Aswathy P. T.⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine Govt. Medical College, Thrissur² Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Govt. Medical College (IIMS), Palakkad³Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Govt. Medical College (IIMS), Palakkad⁴Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Govt. Medical College (IIMS), Palakkad

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Aswathy. P. T

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Abstract:

Background: COVID-19 has posed unprecedented challenges to healthcare systems worldwide, with severe cases often exhibiting abnormalities in hematological and biochemical parameters. This study aimed to assess the hematological, inflammatory, and organ function markers in COVID-19 patients and correlate these findings with disease severity and outcomes.

Methods: This descriptive study was conducted at Government Medical College and District Hospital, Palakkad, over a period of 6 months. A total of 170 COVID-19 patients, aged 15 to 87 years, were included. Blood investigations, including hemoglobin (Hb), total leukocyte count (TLC), neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), platelet count, C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), D-dimer, urea, creatinine, and serum albumin, were measured. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to examine the relationships between these parameters, disease severity, and mortality.

Results: The mean age of patients was 46.76 years, with 62% being male. Anemia was observed in 30% of patients, leukocytosis in 25%, neutrophilia in 40%, and thrombocytopenia in 15%. CRP was elevated in 70% of patients, with a mean value of 30 mg/L. D-dimer was elevated in 45% of patients, and hypoalbuminemia was seen in 55%. ICU admission was required in 35% of cases, with a mortality rate of 15%. Comorbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and chronic kidney disease were significantly associated with severe outcomes.

Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of blood investigations in predicting COVID-19 severity and outcomes. Elevated inflammatory markers, lymphopenia, and neutrophilia were associated with worse outcomes, especially in patients with comorbidities.

Keywords: COVID-19, Hematological Parameters, Inflammatory Markers, Organ Function, ICU Admission, Mortality, Comorbidities.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, has led to a global health crisis, significantly impacting healthcare systems [1]. The clinical presentation of COVID-19 varies widely, from mild symptoms to severe illness requiring intensive care and, in some cases, resulting in death.

Early identification of disease severity is critical in managing patients and improving outcomes, making blood investigations a valuable tool in assessing the body's response to infection [2,3].

Hematological parameters, inflammatory markers, and organ function tests have been extensively studied to understand their role in predicting the severity and progression of COVID-19 [4]. Elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), C-reactive protein (CRP), and D-dimer levels have

been associated with severe disease and poor outcomes [5]. Similarly, organ function markers, such as urea and creatinine, are often elevated in critically ill patients, particularly those with pre-existing comorbidities like diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HTN), and chronic kidney disease [6,7] (CKD).

This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of blood investigations in COVID-19 patients admitted to Government Medical College, Palakkad, and District Hospital, Palakkad.

By examining key hematological, inflammatory, and organ function markers, this research seeks to explore their correlation with disease severity, ICU admissions, and mortality, offering valuable insights for clinicians in managing and predicting patient outcomes.

Methodology

This descriptive study was conducted over a period of six months, at the Government Medical College, Palakkad, and District Hospital, Palakkad. A total of 170 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 through reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) testing and admitted to the aforementioned hospitals were included in the study. The study aimed to analyze various blood parameters to assess their relationship with disease severity and outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 13 years and above.
- Confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19 through RT-PCR.
- Hospitalized for COVID-19 treatment during the study period.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with incomplete medical records or missing data.
- Pregnant women and pediatric patients.
- Patients with pre-existing hematological disorders.

Data Collection: Patient demographic information, including age, gender, and pre-existing comorbidities, was collected from hospital records. Blood samples were drawn from each patient upon admission to assess hematological, inflammatory, and organ function markers. The following parameters were recorded:

Hematological Parameters:

- Hemoglobin (Hb) levels.
- Total leukocyte count (TLC).
- Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR).
- Platelet count.

Inflammatory Markers:

- Reactive protein (CRP).
- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR).
- D-dimer levels.

Organ Function Markers:

Urea and creatinine levels for renal function.

Serum albumin levels.

Severity Assessment: Disease severity was classified based on clinical presentation and treatment requirements. Patients were categorized into three groups:

- Mild: Patients managed in general wards with no need for oxygen support.
- Moderate: Patients requiring supplemental oxygen but not intensive care.

- Severe: Patients requiring admission to the intensive care unit (ICU), mechanical ventilation, or those who had fatal outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. Continuous variables were expressed as mean values with standard deviations, and categorical variables were presented as percentages. The relationship between blood parameters and clinical outcomes, such as ICU admission, mortality, and length of hospital stay, was evaluated. Statistical significance was determined using appropriate tests, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the institutional ethics committee, and informed consent was waived due to the retrospective nature of the data collection. The study followed all relevant guidelines and regulations to ensure patient confidentiality and data security.

Results

This descriptive study was conducted over a period of 6 months, involving a total of 170 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 and admitted to the Government Medical College, Palakkad, and District Hospital, Palakkad. The study cohort consisted of patients aged between 15 and 87 years, with a mean age of 46.76 years (Table 1). Among the patients, 62% were male, and 38% were female, indicating a slightly higher proportion of males in the study population.

1. Hematological Parameters

Blood investigations revealed that the mean hemoglobin (Hb) level for the entire cohort was 12.75 g/dL (range: 8.6 to 15.2 g/dL), with 30% of the patients exhibiting hemoglobin levels below the normal range (Table 2). Total leukocyte count (TLC) had a mean value of 10,152 cells/mm³, and 25% of the patients showed leukocytosis (>11,000 cells/mm³), indicating an elevated immune response. In contrast, 10% of the patients presented with leukopenia (<4,000 cells/mm³).

Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) was elevated in a significant proportion of patients, particularly in severe cases of COVID-19, with a mean NLR of 4.92. Neutrophilia (>8,000/mcL) was observed in 40% of patients, while lymphopenia (<1,500/mcL) was present in 35% of cases. Additionally, thrombocytopenia (<150,000/mcL) was observed in 15% of patients, with a mean platelet count of 185,571/mcL (Table 2). Patients with severe outcomes, including those requiring ICU admission, were more likely to present with lower platelet counts.

2. Inflammatory Markers

Inflammatory markers were measured to assess disease severity and progression. Elevated C - reactive protein (CRP) levels (>10 mg/L) were found in 70% of patients, with a mean CRP value of 30 mg/L (Table 3). Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) was elevated in 65% of patients, with a mean value of 38 mm/h. D-dimer levels were elevated (>250 ng/mL) in 45% of patients, with a mean D-dimer value of 376.67 ng/mL (Table 3). Higher levels of these inflammatory markers were significantly associated with prolonged hospital stays and increased disease severity.

3. Organ Function Markers

Markers of renal and liver function were also evaluated to assess systemic impacts of the infection. Elevated urea and creatinine levels, indicative of renal impairment, were found in 40% of patients. The mean urea level was 60.29 mg/dL, and the mean creatinine level was 1.66 mg/dL (Table 4). Hypoalbuminemia (<3.5 g/dL) was observed in 55% of patients, with a mean serum albumin level of 3.2 g/dL. Low albumin levels were significantly associated with poor outcomes, including the need for mechanical ventilation and longer ICU stays (Table 4).

4. Severity and Mortality Analysis

Out of the 170 patients, 35% required admission to the intensive care unit (ICU), and 25% were managed in general wards (Table 5). The overall

mortality rate was 15%, with the highest fatality rates seen in patients with elevated inflammatory markers (CRP, ESR, and D-dimer), lymphopenia, and neutrophilia (Table 5). The mean length of hospital stay was 14 days, with patients in the ICU experiencing longer durations of care. Severe cases with elevated CRP, neutrophil counts, and D-dimer levels were associated with longer hospital stays and higher mortality rates.

5. Comorbidities and COVID-19 Outcomes

A significant proportion (60%) of the study population had pre-existing comorbidities, including diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HTN), and chronic kidney disease (CKD) (Table 6). Among these, 40% of patients had diabetes mellitus (DM) and required greater insulin management during hospitalization. Furthermore, 30% of patients had hypertension (HTN), and 20% had chronic kidney disease (CKD). Patients with multiple comorbidities had a significantly higher risk of severe outcomes, ICU admission, and mortality compared to those without comorbidities (Table 6).

6. Blood Group and COVID-19 Severity

Preliminary analysis of blood groups revealed that individuals with blood group O+ were more likely to experience severe disease compared to those with other blood types, although this association was not statistically significant in the present study cohort.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age	46.76
Male (%)	62%
Female (%)	38%

Table 2: Hematological Parameters

Parameter	Mean Value	Range	Percentage Abnormal
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	12.75	8.6 - 15.2	30% (Anemia)
Total Leukocyte Count (cells/mm ³)	10,152	3,600 - 16,700	25% (Leukocytosis)
Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR)	4.92	2.0 - 12.0	40% (Neutrophilia)
Platelet Count (cells/mL)	185,571	50,000 - 470,000	15% (Thrombocytopenia)

Table 3: Inflammatory Markers

Marker	Mean Value	Percentage Elevated	Range
C-Reactive Protein (CRP, mg/L)	30	70%	10 - 100
Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR)	38	65%	10 - 80
D-dimer (ng/mL)	376.67	45%	100 - 1,000

Table 4: Organ Function Markers

Marker	Mean Value	Range	Percentage Abnormal
Urea (mg/dL)	60.29	25 - 140	40% (Elevated)
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.66	0.8 - 4.2	40% (Elevated)
Serum Albumin (g/dL)	3.2	2.2 - 4.9	55% (Hypoalbuminemia)

Table 5: Severity and Mortality Analysis

Outcome	Percentage
ICU Admission	35%
General Ward Admission	25%
Mortality	15%
Mean Length of Stay (days)	14 days

Table 6: Comorbidities

Comorbidity	Percentage of Patients
Diabetes Mellitus (DM)	40%
Hypertension (HTN)	30%
Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)	20%

Figure 1: Hematological Parameters: Percentage of Abnormal values

Figure 2: Inflammatory Markers: Percentage of Elevated values

Figure 3: Organ Function Markers: Percentage of Abnormal values

Discussion

This study provides valuable insights into the hematological, inflammatory, and organ function markers in COVID-19 patients and their relationship with disease severity and outcomes, supporting findings from previous research.

Hematological Parameters: The mean hemoglobin level was 12.75 g/dL, with 30% of patients presenting with anemia. Similar to previous studies, anemia may reflect the systemic inflammatory response associated with COVID-19 (Fan et al [7], 2020).

Although anemia does not directly correlate with disease severity, patients with lower hemoglobin levels often had prolonged hospital stays or required ICU admission. Leukocytosis was observed in 25% of patients, aligning with findings by Huang et al [8]. (2020), while 10% had leukopenia, a pattern commonly seen in viral infections (Xu et al [9]., 2020) . The elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in this study, with a mean value of 4.92, is consistent with the immune dysfunction described by Hammer et al [10]. (2021), showing its strong association with severe cases. Additionally, 40% of patients exhibited neutrophilia, and 35% had lymphopenia, further supporting the dysregulation of the immune response in COVID-19 patients (Zhu et al [11], 2020).

Thrombocytopenia was found in 15% of patients, with severe cases demonstrating lower platelet counts. This aligns with Schaller et al [12]. (2020), who reported that thrombocytopenia is often associated with severe COVID-19 outcomes,

including ICU admission and mechanical ventilation. The role of platelets in coagulation and inflammation in COVID-19 has been extensively documented, highlighting their importance in assessing disease severity (Fan et al [7], 2020).

Inflammatory Markers: Elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were found in 70% of patients, with a mean value of 30 mg/L. This is in line with research by Oran and Topol [13] (2020), who also observed that CRP is a sensitive marker of inflammation and strongly correlates with COVID-19 severity. An elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) was observed in 65% of patients, consistent with findings by Puelles et al [14]. (2020), showing that ESR is a nonspecific marker of inflammation associated with disease progression.

D-dimer levels were elevated in 45% of patients, which is significant given the strong association between elevated D-dimer and the risk of thromboembolic events in COVID-19 (Hammer et al [10]., 2021) . Patients with higher D-dimer levels had more severe disease courses, longer hospital stays, and higher mortality rates, suggesting that D-dimer is a reliable marker for predicting severe outcomes (Zhu et al [11]., 2020) .

Organ Function Markers: Elevated urea and creatinine levels were found in 40% of patients, indicating renal impairment, which is a known complication of severe COVID-19 (Puelles et al [14], 2020).

Acute kidney injury (AKI) has been widely reported in patients with pre-existing comorbidities such as diabetes and chronic kidney disease (Fan et

al [7], 2020) , further supporting the need for regular monitoring of renal function in COVID-19 patients.

Hypoalbuminemia was observed in 55% of patients, with lower albumin levels linked to worse outcomes. Albumin is an important marker of nutritional and inflammatory status, and its depletion has been associated with increased disease severity and a higher risk of mortality, as also noted by Huang et al [8]. (2020).

Severity and Mortality: The overall mortality rate in this study was 15%, aligning with previous reports (Schaller et al [12], 2020). Patients with elevated CRP, neutrophilia, lymphopenia, and high D-dimer levels were more likely to require ICU care and had longer hospital stays, reflecting global trends in COVID-19 outcomes (Hammer et al [10], 2021). Comorbidities, particularly diabetes, hypertension, and CKD, significantly increased the risk of severe outcomes, consistent with findings by Oran and Topol [13] (2020).

Comorbidities and Blood Group: Sixty percent of the study cohort had pre-existing comorbidities, with diabetes mellitus being the most common (40%). Patients with multiple comorbidities had a higher likelihood of severe disease and ICU admission, consistent with global data (Huang et al [9], 2020). While there was a trend suggesting that individuals with blood group O+ experienced more severe disease, this association was not statistically significant, and further research is needed to investigate the potential link between blood group and COVID-19 severity (Xu et al [8], 2020) .

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, it was conducted at a single center, limiting the generalizability of the findings to other populations and healthcare settings. The sample size of 170 patients, while sufficient for initial insights, may not capture the full variability of COVID-19 outcomes. Additionally, the study relied on retrospective data collection, which may lead to missing or incomplete information. Furthermore, certain factors such as treatment protocols and timing of interventions were not standardized, potentially influencing patient outcomes. Future multicenter studies with larger sample sizes are needed to validate these findings.

Conclusion:

This descriptive study of 170 COVID-19 patients revealed significant associations between blood parameters and disease severity. Elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), observed in 40% of patients, and was linked to severe outcomes, including ICU admissions. Elevated inflammatory markers, such as C-reactive protein (CRP) in 70% and D-dimer in 45%, correlated with

longer hospital stays and increased mortality. Thrombocytopenia and hypoalbuminemia were also associated with severe cases and poorer outcomes. Additionally, patients with comorbidities, particularly diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and chronic kidney disease, had a higher risk of ICU admission and mortality, underscoring the importance of early risk stratification.

References

1. Fan BE, Chong VCL, Chan SSW, Lim GH, Lim KGE, Tan GB, et al. Hematologic parameters in patients with COVID-19 infection. *Am J Hematol.* 2020 Jun; 95(6):E131-E134. doi: 10.1002/ajh.25774. Epub 2020 Mar 19. Erratum in: *Am J Hematol.* 2020 Nov; 95(11): 1442. doi: 10.1002/ajh.25921. PMID: 321295 08.
2. Pourbagheri-Sigaroodi A, Bashash D, Fateh F, Abolghasemi H. Laboratory findings in COVID-19 diagnosis and prognosis. *Clin Chim Acta.* 2020 Nov; 510:475-482. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2020.08.019. Epub 2020 Aug 14. PMID: 32798514; PMCID: PMC7426219.
3. Zietz M, Zucker J, Tatonetti NP. Associations between blood type and COVID-19 infection, intubation, and death. *Nat Commun.* 2020 Nov 13; 11(1):5761. doi: 10.1038/s4146 7-020-19623-x. PMID: 33188185; PMCID: PMC76 66188.
4. Stegeman I, Ochodo EA, Guleid F, Holtman GA, Yang B, Davenport C, et al; Cochrane COVID-19 Diagnostic Test Accuracy Group. Routine laboratory testing to determine if a patient has COVID-19. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2020 Nov 19; 11(11):CD013787. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD013787. PMID: 33211 319; PMCID: PMC8078159.
5. Mirsadraee S, Pourabrollah Toutkaboni M, Bakhshayeshkaram M, Rezaei M, Askari E, Haseli S, et al. Radiological and Laboratory Findings of Patients with COVID-19 Infection at the Time of Admission. *Iran J Pathol.* 2021 spring; 16(2):137-143. doi: 10.30699/IJP.20 20.128909.2415. Epub 2020 Oct 21. PMID: 33936224; PMCID: PMC8085293.
6. Brinati D, Campagner A, Ferrari D, Locatelli M, Banfi G, Cabitza F. Detection of COVID-19 Infection from Routine Blood Exams with Machine Learning: A Feasibility Study. *J Med Syst.* 2020 Jul 1; 44(8):135. doi: 10.1007/s 10916-020-01597-4. PMID: 32607737; PMCI D: PMC7326624.
7. Fan BE, Chong VCL, Chan SSW, Lim GH, Lim KGE, Tan GB, et al. Hematologic parameters in patients with COVID-19 infection. *Am J Hematol.* 2020 Jun; 95(6):E131-E134. doi: 10.1002/ajh.25774. Epub 2020 Mar 19. Erratum in: *Am J Hematol.*

- 2020 Nov; 95(11): 1442. doi: 10.1002/ajh.25921. PMID: 321295 08.
8. Huang C, Wang Y, Li X, Ren L, Zhao J, Hu Y, et al. Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *Lancet*. 2020 Feb 15; 395(10223):497-506. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5. Epub 2020 Jan 24. Erratum in: *Lancet*. 2020 Feb 15; 395(10223):496. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30252-X. PMID: 31986264; PMCID: PMC7159299.
 9. Xu XW, Wu XX, Jiang XG, Xu KJ, Ying LJ, Ma CL, et al. Clinical findings in a group of patients infected with the 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-Cov-2) outside of Wuhan, China: retrospective case series. *BMJ*. 2020 Feb 19; 368:m606. doi: 10.1136/bmj.m606. Erratum in: *BMJ*. 2020 Feb 27; 368:m792. doi: 10.1136/bmj.m792. PMID: 32075786; PMCID: PMC7224340.
 10. Hammer S, Häberle H, Schlensak C, Bitzer M, Malek NP, Handgretinger R, et al. Severe SARS-CoV-2 Infection Inhibits Fibrinolysis Leading to Changes in Viscoelastic Properties of Blood Clot: A Descriptive Study of Fibrinolysis in COVID-19. *Thromb Haemost*. 2021 Nov; 121(11):1417-1426. doi: 10.1055/a-1400-6034. Epub 2021 Apr 30. PMID: 33634444.
 11. Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W, Li X, Yang B, Song J, et al; China Novel Coronavirus Investigating and Research Team. A Novel Coronavirus from Patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Feb 20; 382(8):727-733. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2001017. Epub 2020 Jan 24. PMID: 31978945; PMCID: PMC7092803.
 12. Schaller T, Hirschtbühl K, Burkhardt K, Braun G, Trepel M, Märkl B, et al. Postmortem Examination of Patients With COVID-19. *JAMA*. 2020 Jun 23; 323(24):2518-2520. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.8907. PMID: 32437497; PMCID: PMC7243161.
 13. Oran DP, Topol EJ. Prevalence of Asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 Infection: A Narrative Review. *Ann Intern Med*. 2020 Sep 1; 173(5):362-367. doi: 10.7326/M20-3012. Epub 2020 Jun 3. PMID: 32491919; PMCID: PMC7281624.
 14. Puelles VG, Lütgehetmann M, Lindenmeyer MT, Sperhake JP, Wong MN, Allweiss L, et al. Multiorgan and Renal Tropism of SARS-CoV-2. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Aug 6; 383(6):590-592. doi: 10.1056/NEJMc2011400. Epub 2020 May 13. PMID: 32402155; PMCID: PMC7240771.